

Comparative Study of Hemodynamic Changes during the Insertion of Laryngeal Mask Airway and Endotracheal Intubation

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Abstract:

Introduction: Airway management is of prime importance during delivery of general anaesthesia. Patients, who have been anaesthetized, are unable to maintain an adequate airway on their own and artificial airway maintenance devices are employed. Aims of the study are to compare classic LMA with endotracheal portex cuffed tube intubation in 60 patients undergoing surgeries under general anaesthesia

Methods: This prospective, randomized clinical study was carried over a period of two and half years. 60 patients aged 20-60 years, belonging to ASA grade I-II scheduled for elective surgical procedure were included in this study. Informed written consent was obtained from each patient and the procedure was explained to the patients. All the quantitative data were analyzed using unpaired t-test. The results were expressed, as Mean + SD. 'P' value < 0.05 was taken as statistically significant

Results: This prospective randomized clinical study comprised of 60 patients belonging to ASA Grade I - II undergoing elective surgical procedure. 30 patients were studied with Group A (LMA classic) and 30 patients were studied as a Group B (ETT). No. of attempts, ease of insertion, hemodynamics response and other relevant parameters were studied and analyzed.

Conclusion: We concluded that LMA classic is safe and useful alternative to endotracheal intubation in elective fasted adult patients undergoing elective surgeries under general anaesthesia. It is judge by stable haemodynamic, adequate oxygenation & ventilation and ease of insertion.

Keywords: Hemodynamic Changes, Laryngeal Mask Airway, Endotracheal Intubation, Anesthesia.

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Introduction

Airway management is of prime importance during delivery of general anaesthesia. Patients, who have been anaesthetized, are unable to maintain an adequate airway on their own and artificial airway maintenance devices are employed. Traditionally, laryngoscopy and endotracheal intubation have been the mainstay in providing adequate airway management, delivering anaesthesia and avoidance of aspiration in anaesthetized patients. Though intubation has many advantages including provision of a reliable airway, prevention of aspiration and delivery of anaesthetic gases, it is not without com-

plications [1]. The choice of securing the airway during general anaesthesia often lies between endotracheal intubation and insertion of the laryngeal mask airway. It has been hypothesized that both are associated with some degree of pressure responses due to reflex sympathetic discharge in response to laryngotracheal stimulation, which in turn leads to increased catecholamine release. These hemodynamic changes are probably of little significance in normal, healthy individuals, but may be more severe or even dangerous in patients with underlying co-morbidities. It may lead to complications

like myocardial infarction, left ventricular failure, cerebro vascular accidents, intracranial hypertension and rise in intra ocular pressure [2,3,4]. Many methods have been utilized to attenuate the pressure responses following the insertion of endotracheal tube like increasing the depth of anaesthesia and various pharmacological approaches, which include the use of lignocaine, esmolol, nitroglycerine, verapamil, nicardipine and diltiazem. Use of laryngeal mask airway in place of endotracheal tube has been observed to have less hemodynamic responses after its insertion, as its insertion requires neither visualisation of cords nor the penetration of larynx. There are plenty of studies in literature on the hemodynamic responses to endotracheal intubation when compared to laryngeal mask airway. Based on these facts, we intend to investigate the hemodynamic changes with LMA (LMA-classic) vs endotracheal tube among patients undergoing general anesthesia posted for elective surgery and to determine if laryngeal mask airway could be an acceptable alternative airway device to endotracheal tube in our hospital setup, where there is a trend of using endotracheal tube. Aims of the study are to compare classic LMA with endotracheal portex cuffed tube intubation in 60 patients undergoing surgeries under general anesthesia with respect to time and attempts taken for insertion, ease of insertion, and to compare hemodynamic changes during insertion of device.

Material & Method

This prospective, randomized clinical study was carried over a period of two and half years. 60 patients aged 20-60 years, belonging to ASA grade I-II scheduled for elective surgical procedure were included in this study. Informed written consent was obtained from each patient and the procedure was explained to the patients.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with History of Cardiac Diseases like Angina; previous history or ECG evidence of myocardial infarction, Drug History: on β blockers, steroid, History of endocrinal diseases like hyperthyroidism and diabetes mellitus, History of respiratory diseases like COPD, other disease like gastro esophageal reflux, obesity and undergoing emergency procedures.

Pre-operative Assessment: Pre-operative assessment was done a day before the planned surgery. Any significant past, family and personal history were taken. General and systemic examination were done, vitals (heart rate, blood pressure, and respiratory rate) and investigations were noted. Weight, height and BMI were noted. Airway assessment was done with mallampati classification.

Technique:

- 60 patients undergoing elective surgical proce-

dures were randomized into two groups. Each group included 30 patients.

- Group A patients were inserted classical LMA device.
- Group B patients were inserted endotracheal cuffed tube.
- On the day of surgery, the patients were taken to the operating room, intravenous cannula inserted. ECG monitor, pulse oximeter and NIBP were attached, and data noted.
- After insertion of LMA classic, Cuff was inflated with air as per manufactures instructions, EtCO₂ was attached, and bilateral chest movement; square wave capnography during manual ventilation and no audible leak with peak airway pressure less than 20 mm Hg confirmed correct placement of device.
- Times taken for insertion were noted. It is the time between the picking up the airway device and obtaining effective airway.
- Numbers of attempts were recorded, 3rd attempt considered as a failure of insertion of device.

Ease of Insertion: Group A: LMA, Size: 3/4, Group B: Endotracheal Intubation, Size: 7-9

Monitoring: Pulse/min, Blood pressure in mmHg EtCO₂, ECG monitoring, and SpO₂

Haemodynamic Changes: Heart rate, Blood Pressure, oxygen saturation and EtCO₂ were recorded at various intervals - Pre-operative and 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 minutes after procedure

Extubation: At the end of surgery, anesthetic agent was discontinued. When the patients awakened (facial grimace, adequate tidal volume, ability to open eye) LMA classic/ Tracheal tube were removed after full deflation of cuff and thorough oral suction. After removal of LMA classic or tracheal extubation, 100% O₂ was administered through a facemask. All the quantitative data were analyzed using unpaired t-test. The results were expressed as Mean \pm SD. 'P' value < 0.05 was taken as statistically significant and 'P' values <0.001 were taken as highly significant.

Results

This prospective randomized clinical study comprised of 60 patients belonging to ASA Grade I - II undergoing elective surgical procedure. 30 patients were studied with Group A (LMA classic) and 30 patients were studied as a Group B (ETT). The data was collected, compiled and analyzed statistically. All continuous variables are reported as Mean \pm Standard deviation. Group comparisons of normally distributed variable were tested by unpaired 't' test. 'P' value of 0.05 or less was considered to indicate a statistically significant difference for all statistical tests.

Table 1: Demographic data

Variable	LMA (M + SD)	ETT (M + SD)
Age (Years)	40.23±10.48	39.33±11.1
Height (cm)	149±3.30	149±3.76
Weight (kg)	49±2.67	50±3.79
BMI (Kg/M ²)	22±1.03	22±1.44
Sex : Male	17	15
: Female	13	15
Duration of surgery	38±17.50	39.17±17.67

Table-1 shows the demographic data of both group. There were no significant difference between groups regarding to Age, BMI, ASA grade and Duration of surgery.

Table 2: No. of attempts

	LMA	ETT
1 st attempt	24	24
2 nd attempt	6	6

Table-2 shows number of attempts for both groups. There were no statistically significant differences between both groups.

Table 3: Time for insertion

	LMA	ETT	P value
Effective airway insertion time (sec)	10.83±2.89	11.43±3.54	0.303

Table- 3 shows effective insertion time for both groups. There were no statistically significant differences between both groups.

Table 4: Ease of insertion

Ease of insertion	LMA		ETT	
	No	%	No	%
Easy	26	86.66	23	76.66
Difficult	04	13.33	07	23.33
Failed	00	00	00	00
Total	30	100	30	100

Table- 4 shows Ease of insertion is more with Group A (86.66) than Group B (76.66).

Table 5: Pulse Rate

	LMA (M+/-SD)	ETT (M+/- SD)	P Value
Pre-op	80.87±7.13	79.70±8.56	0.566
After premedication	83.10±10.26	83.20±7.81	0.966
1 min after procedure	84.76±10.47	92.35±8.67	0.002
2 min after procedure	79.78±9.85	85.70±8.05	0.011
3 min after procedure	73.96±9.13	80.70±7.58	0.002
5min after procedure	69.80±8.62	74.88±7.03	0.012
10 min after procedure	68.97±8.52	72.38±6.80	0.086

Table- 5 shows mean pulse rate at various interval in both groups. Preoperative and Baseline reading were comparable in both groups. After insertion at 1, 2, 3, 5 min; Pulse rate was increased in group B (ETT) group, as compared to group A (LMA). Pulse rates were comparable at 10 minutes after insertion. The increase in the pulse rate was statistically significant (P<0.05) at 1, 2, 3 and 5 min after insertions.

Table 6: Systolic Blood Pressure

TIME	LMA (M+/-SD)	ETT (M+/-SD)	P Value
Pre-op	134.07±11.04	133.07±12.92	0.7471
After premedication	130.37±11.64	130.43±12.49	0.9829
1 min after procedure	136.89±12.22	151.30±14.49	0.0000
2 min after procedure	121.24±10.82	131.74±12.61	0.0005
3 min after procedure	106.90±9.54	117.39±11.24	0.0003
5min after procedure	97.78±8.73	109.56±10.49	0.0000
10 min after procedure	95.17±8.50	108.26±10.37	0.0000

Table- 6 shows changes in mean systolic blood pressure at various periods in both groups. Preoperative and Baseline reading were comparable in both

groups. After insertion at 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 min; SBP was increased in group B (ETT) group, as compared to group A (LMA). The increase in the

SBP was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) at 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 min after insertions.

Table 7: Diastolic Blood Pressure

TIME	LMA(M+/-SD)	ETT (M+/-SD)	P Value
Pre-op	83.63±10.89	82.67±9.31	0.7117
After premedication	79.67±11.63	80.50±10.05	0.7664
1 min after procedure	84.45±12.32	92.58±11.55	0.0084
2 min after procedure	64.53±9.42	81.31±10.15	0.0000
3 min after procedure	55.77±8.14	68.43±8.54	0.0000
5 min after procedure	53.38±7.79	66.82±8.34	0.0000
10 min after procedure	50.19±7.33	65.21±8.14	0.0000

Table- 7 shows mean diastolic blood pressure at various periods in both groups. Preoperative and Baseline reading were comparable in both groups. After insertion at 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 min; DBP was

increased in group B (ETT) group, as compared to group A (LMA). The increase in the DBP was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) at 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 min after insertions.

Table 8: Mean Arterial Blood Pressure

TIME	LMA (M+/-SD)	ETT (M+/- SD)	P Value
Pre-op	100.44±10.48	99.47±10.08	0.7126
After premedication	96.57±11.00	97.14±10.44	0.8346
1 min after procedure	101.93±11.62	112.15±12.04	0.0008
2 min after procedure	83.43±9.33	98.12±10.54	0.0000
3 min after procedure	75.85±8.36	84.75±9.07	0.0000
5 min after procedure	68.18±7.65	81.06±8.70	0.0000
10 min after procedure	65.18±7.28	79.56±8.53	0.0000

Table- 8 shows mean arterial blood pressure at various periods in both groups. Preoperative and Baseline reading were comparable in both groups. After insertion at 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 min; DBP was increased in group B (ETT) group, as compared to group A (LMA). The increase in the DBP was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) at 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 min after insertions.

Discussion

Laryngoscopy and endotracheal intubation results in sympathetic stimulation that leads to hypertension and tachycardia. Such changes can cause hemodynamic instability during the crucial period of anaesthesia induction. Both the laryngoscopy and intubation separately results in sympathetic stimulation but the catecholamine rise with intubation exceeds that with laryngoscopy alone [5]. Hence, the need to attenuate the sympathetic response to laryngoscopy and intubation is important.

Present being the era of minimal invasiveness; no wonder supraglottic airway devices have gained popularity. They are the golden mean between the facemask and endotracheal intubation in terms of both anatomical position and degree of invasiveness. As they require neither laryngoscopy nor visualization of glottis, they reduce the stress response as compared to laryngoscopy and intubation and during emergence from anaesthesia. They can be easily inserted in the patients with cervical spine injury and provide an effective tool for ventilation in difficult airway scenario.

This study was conducted with the aim of comparing hemodynamic changes following insertion of LMA classic and ETT as an airway device. Our study included 60 adult patients belonging to ASA grade I & II between the ages of 20-60 years, weighing between 40-70 kg posted for elective surgical procedure under general anaesthesia.

Demographic data: There was no significant difference in demographic data between the two groups. The mean age was 40.23±10.48 years in group A & 39.33±11.1 years in group B. The mean weight was 49±2.67 in group A & 50±3.79 in group B. The mean BMI was 22.01±1.03 in group A and 22±1.44 in group B. The size of LMA was chosen according to weight of the patient. In our study, we compared LMA & ETT with respect to time taken for insertion, attempts taken, ease of insertion and hemodynamic responses to insertion at various intervals.

Time taken for insertion: Khalid, K.J. et al [1] found that it took a significantly shorter time to insert an LMA (12.63 sec) as compared to time taken to insert an ETT (22.76 sec). Namita Saraswat et al [6] found that mean time taken for successful placement was 15.77 s and 16.93 s for PLMA and ETT group respectively.

In our study, the mean time taken for successful placement was 10.83±2.89 s and 11.43±3.54 s for Group A (LMA) and Group B (ETT) respectively. There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups and P value was 0.307 (> 0.05).

Ease of insertion: Khalid, K.J. et al [1] found that insertion of an LMA was rated easy in 84% of the patients while it was rated easy in 60% of the ETT patients.

Bimla Sharma et al [7] found that PLMA was easy to insert with higher success rate (86.67%) in first attempt than ETT (83.33%).

In our study, ease of insertion was more with LMA (86.66%) than ETT (76.66%). There was difficult insertion in 23.33% of patients in group B (ETT). There were no failed insertions in any patients in both the groups.

Hemodynamic changes: Bhattacharya D et al(8): The results showed that increase in systolic and diastolic blood pressure following endotracheal intubation (group A) was much more as compared to LMA (group B) ($p < 0.01$). The increase in heart rate from baseline value was more in endotracheal intubation group than in LMA ($P < 0.05$). To conclude, insertion of LMA was associated with lesser pressure response as compared to endotracheal intubation in patients with controlled hypertension. It is an effective method to avoid laryngoscopic pressure response during endotracheal intubation in hypertensive patients.

Fujii Y et al [9]: The hemodynamic changes were greater after intubation than after LMA insertion ($P < 0.05$). Following intubation of the trachea or insertion of the LMA, HR increased more markedly in hypertensive patients than in normotensive patients ($P < 0.05$). Plasma adrenaline and noradrenaline concentrations after tracheal intubation or LMA insertion increased compared with baseline values ($P < 0.05$) in normotensive and hypertensive patients. The increase in noradrenaline concentration after tracheal intubation was greater than that after LMA insertion ($P < 0.05$). No patient revealed ECG evidence of myocardial ischemia. Lee Y et al [10] found that the changes of blood pressure and heart rate exhibited a similar but attenuated pattern of response with laryngeal mask insertion in comparison with tracheal intubation. In sum, laryngeal mask insertion may therefore offer some advantages over tracheal intubation in the anesthetic management of hypertensive patients, in whom less pressure response is of particular concern.

Braude N et al [11] concluded that attenuated pattern of response was associated with mask insertion in comparison with laryngoscopy and intubation; significant differences between the groups were evident in arterial diastolic blood pressure immediately after insertion and again 2 minutes later. Use of the laryngeal mask may therefore offer some limited advantages over tracheal intubation in the anesthetic management of patients where the avoidance of the pressure response is of particular concern.

Wood ML et al [12] concluded that the changes in all cardiovascular parameters measured following LMA insertion were significantly less ($P < 0.05$) when compared with those following laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation.

Rooke GO et al [13]: They found that blood pressure and heart rate decreased equally in both groups after induction of anesthesia. Hemodynamic variables increased after tracheal intubation but were unchanged after laryngeal mask insertion ($P < 0.05$ for intergroup differences). Heart rate, but not blood pressure, increased above baseline levels in the tracheal intubation group.

S. R. Bennett et al [14] found that intubation caused an increase in MAP compared with that caused by LMA ($P < 0.05$). Mixed venous oxygen saturation increased in the intubated patients but not with the LMA ($P < 0.05$). HR did not change at induction in the LMA group. Changes at extubation were similar in all groups but cardiac index was lower in the LMA group ($P < 0.05$).

Martin Kahl et al [15] concluded that reduction of cardiovascular and endocrine stress response associated with endotracheal intubation is more pronounced when performed via the intubating laryngeal mask as compared to conventional direct laryngoscopy. Thus, this technique can be helpful in high-risk cardiac patients.

Khalid, K.J. et al [1] found that the changes in hemodynamic parameters after laryngoscopy and ETT insertion were significantly greater than those elicited by LMA insertion ($p < 0.0001$). The increase took about 5 minutes to return to pre insertion values in the ETT group, while it took about 3 minutes for the same values to return to pre insertion values in the LMA group. It took a significantly shorter time to insert an LMA (12.63 sec) as compared to time taken to insert an ETT (22.76 sec). Insertion of an LMA was rated easy in 84% of the patients while it was rated easy in 60% of the ETT patients. In our study, the hemodynamic responses were lower for the placement of LMA than ETT. The mean pulse rate increased from baseline value (after premedication) of 83.10 ± 10.26 to 84.76 ± 10.47 and 83.20 ± 7.81 to 92.35 ± 8.67 after the placement of LMA and ETT intubation respectively. The increase in pulse rate was more in endotracheal group as compared to LMA classic group.

The increase in pulse rate was statistically significant even at 5 minutes after insertion. After insertion, there was an increase in mean SBP from a baseline value of before insertion 130.37 ± 11.64 to 136.89 ± 12.22 in LMA and 130.43 ± 12.49 to 151.30 ± 14.49 in ETT. The increase in the systolic blood pressure was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) at 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 minutes after insertion. After insertion, there was an increase in mean DBP from a baseline value of before insertion 79.67 ± 11.63 to

84.45±12.32 in LMA and 80.50±10.05 to 92.58±11.55 in ETT. The increase in the diastolic blood pressure was statistically significant ($P<0.05$) at 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 minutes after insertion. The MAP increased from a baseline value of 96.57±11.00 to 101.93±11.62 before insertion and 97.14±10.44 to 112.15±12.04 after the placement of LMA and ETT respectively. The increase in the MAP was statistically significant ($P<0.05$) at 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 minutes after insertion.

SPO₂ and ETCO₂: Jaya lavani et al [16] found that there were no significant difference in mean SpO₂ and EtCO₂ level recorded at different time interval. In our study, there was no significant difference in SpO₂ recorded at different time interval in both groups.

Conclusion

We had organized randomized clinical comparative study of LMA classic and endotracheal tube intubation in 60 patients aged 20-60 years and weighing 40-70 kg belonging to ASA grade I-II scheduled for elective surgical procedure under general anaesthesia. We studied and compared the time taken for insertion; number of attempts taken to insert the device; ease of insertion; hemodynamic responses preoperatively, after premedication and at 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 minutes after procedure. The mean time taken, for successful placement of airway device were comparable in both the groups. There were no statistically significant differences between two groups. Ease of insertion was more with LMA than ETT. The haemodynamic response of LMA was less during insertion as compared to laryngoscopy and intubation in ETT group. There were no differences in mean SpO₂ recorded at different time interval in both groups. We concluded that LMA classic is safe and useful alternative to endotracheal intubation in elective fasted adult patients undergoing elective surgeries under general anaesthesia. It is judge by stable haemodynamic, adequate oxygenation & ventilation and ease of insertion.

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